
Demographic Correlates of Social Media Engagement with Governance Issues among Edo State Residents

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Abstract

This study examined the demographic correlates of social media engagement with governance issues among Edo State residents, investigating how factors such as age, gender, education and socioeconomic status influence participation in online governance discourse. Using a descriptive survey research design, data were collected from 400 respondents via an online questionnaire. Findings revealed that while social media serves as a major source of political information, active discussion and engagement with governance content vary significantly across demographic lines. Regression analysis results indicated that gender ($\beta = 0.216, p < 0.05$), age ($\beta = -0.189, p < 0.05$), and education level ($\beta = 0.315, p < 0.01$) significantly influence social media participation in governance discourse, with men and older individuals engaging more frequently. Additionally, results showed that 62.3% of respondents use social media to access governance-related content, but only 38.7% actively engage in discourse. The findings provided valuable insights for policymakers, civil society organisations and researchers aiming to foster inclusive digital democracy in Nigeria.

Keywords: Social Media Engagement, Governance Issues, Demographic Correlates, Political Participation, Edo State Residents

Introduction

Social media engagement with governance-related issues has become a critical area of focus in contemporary political communication. Governance, defined as the process by which public institutions manage resources, conduct public affairs and implement policies in a transparent, accountable, participatory and effective manner (World Bank, 1992), remains a central mechanism for societal development and transformation. The way in which people access information related to governance plays a crucial role in shaping public perception, ensuring government responsiveness and fostering civic participation (Norris, 2001). Recognising this, Rhodes (1996) argues that governance extends beyond government institutions to encompass decision-making and policy execution involving collaboration between public authorities, private sector entities, and civil society actors. This perspective highlights the evolving nature of governance, where non-state actors play an increasing role in shaping policies and public administration (Kooiman, 2003). In the digital age, social media has become a powerful tool for enhancing governance by promoting transparency, facilitating direct engagement between governments and citizens, and enabling real-time public discourse on policy issues (Meijer, 2012).

The increasing role of social media in governance and civic engagement has sparked widespread academic interest, particularly in understanding the demographic factors influencing social media usage for governance-related discussions. Social media platforms have transformed public discourse, enabling citizens to engage with government policies, electoral processes, and accountability measures in real time (Pew Research, 2021). With platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, and Instagram becoming central to political conversations, it is crucial to examine the extent to which demographic characteristics (such as age, gender, education, and socioeconomic status) shape patterns of engagement with governance issues.

Several studies have explored social media usage trends and their demographic correlates. Pew Research (2021) found that younger adults exhibit the highest engagement levels across multiple social media platforms, while older populations demonstrate relatively lower adoption rates. The study also revealed significant gender differences, with women being more active on platforms such as Pinterest and Facebook, while men prefer LinkedIn and Reddit. Similarly, Pearce & Rice (2020) conducted a meta-analysis on sociodemographic factors affecting social media adoption, concluding that individuals with higher education levels and income were more likely to engage in digital platforms. Their findings suggested that urban residents were more engaged in online discussions compared to rural populations, indicating a possible disparity in digital access and usage patterns.

Statement of the Problem

Social media has become an indispensable tool for political participation, governance discussions and civic activism in Nigeria. However, little is known about the specific demographic factors that shape engagement levels with governance issues among Edo State residents. While existing studies (Pew Research, 2021; Pearce & Rice, 2020; Greenwood & Perrin, 2020) have explored global and Western trends, their findings may not be directly applicable to Edo State, where socioeconomic disparities, political dynamics, and internet accessibility vary significantly from those in developed countries. The lack of empirical data on how age, gender, education, and economic status influence social media-driven governance engagement in Edo State presents a critical gap in understanding digital political participation at a localised level. Furthermore, factors such as political interest, trust in government, and digital literacy remain underexplored as potential mediating variables in the relationship between demographic factors and social media engagement. This study was, therefore, carried out to fill this gap by examining the demographic correlates of social media engagement with governance issues among Edo State residents.

Research Questions

In line with the Gaps observed in research, the following Research questions are raised for this study:

1. What is the frequency of engagement of sampled Edo residents with political and governance issues on social media?
2. What are the demographic correlates of social media engagement with political and governance issues on social media?

Review of Relevant Literature

In the digital age, social media has emerged as a transformative force in reshaping how citizens interact with governance. No longer confined to traditional town halls or bureaucratic channels, governance discussions now unfold in the dynamic, interactive spaces of platforms like Twitter, WhatsApp, and Facebook. These platforms have democratized access to political discourse, enabling citizens to engage directly with government actors, voice their concerns, and participate in decision-making processes. However, the nature of this engagement is not uniform; it is shaped by the affordances of each platform, the modes of interaction they enable, and the demographic characteristics of their users. This conceptual framework seeks to unravel these complexities by examining how different engagement modes (commenting, liking, sharing, and direct messaging) influence governance discourse, how platform-specific features shape participation, and how age demographics mediate platform preferences and engagement styles.

The 2010s marked a turning point, as rapid advancements in technology, increased internet penetration, and the affordability of smartphones led to a surge in social media usage. Political figures and parties recognized the potential of these platforms in reaching a broader audience and engaging with supporters (Nwokora & Akinyemi, 2019). The 2015 general elections highlighted this shift, as social media became a crucial tool for political mobilization. Muhammadu Buhari's campaign, for example, strategically used Twitter with hashtags like #GMB15 to promote his candidacy and engage with voters (Ibrahim & Ajibade, 2019).

The interactive affordances of Web 2.0, such as user-generated content, real-time feedback, and peer-to-peer communication, fostered an environment in which individuals were no longer just consumers of digital content but also active participants in shaping the flow of information. Platforms like Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and Instagram exemplified this transformation, as they allowed users to publish their own content while engaging with others through likes, comments, shares, and discussions (Boyd & Ellison, 2007). Social media engagement refers to the ways users interact with content on social media platforms, including likes, shares, comments, and participation in discussions (Kushin & Yamamoto, 2010). It reflects the level of involvement, interaction, and influence that social media users have in online spaces. Engagement can be active, such as posting and commenting, or passive, such as viewing and liking content (Men & Tsai, 2013). Cvijikj & Michahelles, (2013) described social media engagement as the degree to which users interact with a brand, individual, or organization through digital platforms, manifesting in measurable activities like reactions, retweets, and direct messaging. It is considered a critical metric for assessing social media effectiveness and audience responsiveness (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010).

Pew Research (2021) carried out a study to assess the prevalence of social media usage among U.S. adults and identify patterns of engagement across different platforms. The study employed a survey method, collecting data from 1,502 U.S. adults aged 18 and older through landline and cellphone interviews between January 25 and February 8, 2021. The sample was weighted to match the U.S. adult population using the 2019 American Community Survey and census data. The findings revealed that approximately 72% of U.S. adults reported using social media. Among specific platforms, YouTube

(81%) and Facebook (69%) emerged as the most widely used, followed by Instagram (40%), Pinterest (31%), LinkedIn (28%), Snapchat (25%), Twitter (23%), WhatsApp (23%), TikTok (21%), and Nextdoor (13%). The study also found that age significantly influenced social media adoption, with younger adults (18–29 years) being the most active users, while engagement rates declined among older demographics (Pew Research, 2021).

Pearce and Rice (2020) conducted a meta-analysis examining the relationship between sociodemographic factors and social media adoption. The study synthesized data from 24 independent studies, focusing on variables such as age, gender, education, income, and urban versus rural residency. Their findings indicated that females, younger individuals, those with higher education levels and income, and urban residents were more likely to adopt social media. Specifically, younger individuals exhibited a greater likelihood of engaging with social media platforms, while older users showed lower adoption rates. Women were found to be more active on social media than men, and individuals with higher educational attainment demonstrated increased engagement across various platforms. Income levels also played a role, as those in higher income brackets had greater access to digital platforms, while rural residents lagged in adoption compared to their urban counterparts (Pearce & Rice, 2020).

Collectively, these studies underscore the significant influence of demographic factors on social media adoption and engagement. Age remains a predominant determinant, with younger users engaging more frequently, while older users demonstrate lower participation rates. Gender and socioeconomic status also shape platform preferences, highlighting the need for tailored digital strategies in governance, marketing, and civic engagement. As social media continues to evolve, understanding these demographic correlates will be essential for researchers, policymakers, and businesses aiming to leverage digital platforms effectively.

Theoretical Framework

The study on demographic correlates of social media engagement with governance issues among Edo State residents can be anchored on several theories that explain how individuals adopt and use digital platforms for civic participation. Among these, the Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT), Digital Divide Theory, and Political Participation Theory provide strong theoretical grounding by explaining the motivations, accessibility barriers, and participatory behaviors that influence engagement with governance issues on social media.

Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT) – Blumler & Katz (1974)

The Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT) posits that individuals actively select media platforms based on their specific needs and expectations (Blumler & Katz, 1974). Unlike earlier media theories that viewed audiences as passive consumers, UGT emphasises that people engage with media for different purposes, including information-seeking, entertainment, social interaction, and political participation. In the context of this study, UGT helps explain why different demographic groups in Edo State engage with governance-related content on social media. For instance, younger individuals may use

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platforms like Twitter and Instagram to stay informed about government policies, while older adults might prefer Facebook or WhatsApp to discuss governance issues within their social circles. Similarly, individuals with higher education levels may engage in governance discourse for political awareness and activism, while those with lower education levels may primarily use social media for entertainment or social networking. By applying UGT, this study can explore the motivations behind social media engagement with governance issues and determine whether demographic factors such as age, gender, education, and socioeconomic status influence why and how individuals participate in governance discussions online.

Digital Divide Theory – Norris (2001)

The Digital Divide Theory explains disparities in access to and use of digital technologies, highlighting inequalities based on socioeconomic status, education, geography and generational differences (Norris, 2001). It is divided into two levels:

First-Level Digital Divide – Differences in access to internet and digital devices.

Second-Level Digital Divide – Differences in digital literacy and ability to engage meaningfully with online content.

This theory is crucial for understanding why some demographic groups in Edo State may engage more actively in governance-related discussions on social media than others. For example, urban residents with higher income and education levels may have better access to smartphones, stable internet and digital literacy training, enabling them to participate more effectively in online governance debates. In contrast, rural residents or individuals from lower-income households may experience limited internet access or lack the necessary digital skills, restricting their ability to engage in governance issues online. By integrating the Digital Divide Theory, this study can examine how accessibility and digital literacy disparities affect the level of engagement with governance-related content among different demographic groups in Edo State. It will also help identify barriers preventing effective participation, such as cost of internet data, lack of technical knowledge, or limited government transparency on digital platforms.

Political Participation Theory – Verba, Schlozman, & Brady (1995)

The Political Participation Theory explains the factors that drive individuals to engage in political activities, including voting, activism, and discussions on governance (Verba, Schlozman & Brady, 1995). The theory identifies three primary factors influencing political participation:

Resources – Includes education, income, and access to information, which determine an individual's ability to engage in political discussions.

Psychological Engagement – Factors such as political awareness, trust in government, and civic responsibility influence an individual's willingness to engage.

Recruitment Networks – The role of peers, organisations, and digital influencers in mobilising individuals for political engagement.

Applying this theory to the study, social media serves as a modern-day recruitment tool that mobilises citizens to participate in governance discussions. However, engagement levels may vary across demographic groups. For instance, younger, digitally literate individuals may be more likely to use Twitter or Facebook for political discussions, advocacy, or protests, while older or less-educated individuals may be less politically active online due to a lack of trust in government or limited awareness of digital platforms.

This theory is relevant because it helps explain why some demographic groups in Edo State are more politically active on social media than others. It also provides insights into whether social media platforms are used for mere political expression or actual political mobilisation, which can inform strategies for increasing inclusive civic engagement in governance discussions.

These three theories (UGT, Digital Divide Theory, and Political Participation Theory) work together to explain the demographic correlates of social media engagement with governance issues in Edo State. UGT explains why people engage with governance-related content on social media, Digital Divide Theory highlights who is more likely to participate based on access and digital literacy, and Political Participation Theory explores how demographic characteristics influence the level of civic engagement online. By integrating these theories, this study will provide a comprehensive framework for understanding the patterns, barriers, and motivations influencing social media engagement with governance among Edo State residents. This knowledge will be valuable for policymakers, civic organizations, and digital advocacy groups seeking to bridge the digital divide, enhance online political participation, and ensure more inclusive governance discussions on social media platforms.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The survey method was considered appropriate for this study as it allowed the researcher to gather large amounts of data from a population at a single point in time. Descriptive research design helped identify the patterns of social media consumption, levels of critical democratic citizenship, and engagement with governance issues among residents of Edo state (Creswell & Creswell, 2023). The use of a structured questionnaire enables efficient data collection and quantitative analysis.

According to Datareportal's Digital 2023 Report, Nigeria had approximately 36.9 million social media users as of January 2023, representing about 17.1% of the population. Nigeria has one of the highest social media penetration rates in Africa, with platforms like Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter (now X), and Instagram being widely used. Edo State has an estimated population of 4.8 million people (based on the National Population Commission of Nigeria projections for 2023). Assuming the social media penetration rate in Edo State is similar to the national average (17.1%), the estimated number of social media users in Edo State would be around 820,000. Social media usage is higher in urban areas compared to rural areas.

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Edo State, with its capital Benin City being a major urban center, likely has a higher concentration of social media users compared to rural areas. If we assume a higher penetration rate of 20-25% in urban areas, the number of social media users in Edo State could range between 960,000 to 1.2 million. Based on the national social media penetration rate and Edo State's population, the estimated number of social media users in Edo State is approximately 820,000 to 1.2 million. However, this is a rough estimate, and the actual number could vary depending on factors such as internet accessibility, smartphone penetration, and urban-rural disparities.

Using Cochran's formula:

$$n = (Z^2 X p X (1 - p)) / e^2$$

Where:

Z = 1.96 (for a 95% confidence level)

p = 0.5 (maximum variability, since the exact proportion is unknown)

e = 0.05 (margin of error)

Using this formula, the calculated sample size is approximately 385, which is often rounded up to 400 for convenience. Thus, a sample size of 400 is appropriate for drawing statistically significant conclusions about the social media user population in Edo State. To achieve a representative sample of the population across Edo State, a sample size of 400 respondents was selected. This sample size meets recommendations for survey research with large populations, allowing for generalizability and reliable statistical analysis (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2019).

To distribute the sample of 400 social media users across Edo State for research, several factors were considered, including urbanization, population density, and social media adoption rates. The following table presents the proposed sample distribution based on these factors.

Table 1: Showing the Sample Frame

Category	LGAs Included	Percentage of Sample	Sample Size
Urban Areas	Benin City (Oredo, Egor, Ikpoba-Okha)	50%	200
Semi-Urban Areas	Auchi, Ekpoma, Uromi, Irrua	30%	120
Rural Areas	Other 14 LGAs	20%	80

Benin City (Oredo, Egor, Ikpoba-Okha) is the most urbanized and digitally connected area, warranting a larger sample allocation.

Semi-urban areas like Auchi, Ekpoma, and Uromi have growing internet access, making them relevant for the study. Rural areas have lower social media adoption, so a smaller sample size is assigned to reflect usage trends. The primary instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire. The instrument was designed to elicit responses on the demographic variables of respondents in Edo state and to measure the frequency of engagement with political and governance issues on social media. The demographic variables are age, Sex, Educational qualification, occupation and religion of respondents. The scale for frequency of engagement with political and governance issues on social media is an adapted scale from Gil de Zúñiga, Jung & Valenzuela (2012). It is a four item

scale with the following variables “I use social media daily to stay informed about political and governance issues, I spend a significant amount of time on social media platforms discussing current events and governance,.” I follow social media accounts that focus on political or governmental matters, I regularly engage with news content shared by my social media contacts. Responses are elicited on a likert scale.

To ensure content validity for the CDCS, the instrument was distributed to a panel of experts from the fields of political science, public administration, and social media research reviewed the questionnaire. The experts evaluated each item for relevance, clarity, and alignment with the constructs of engagement with political and governance issues. The expert panel rated each item on a scale of 1 to 4 (1 = Not relevant, 2 = somewhat relevant, 3 = Relevant, 4 = Very relevant). The Content Validity Index (CVI) was then calculated to assess the proportion of items rated as relevant by the experts. A CVI score of 0.86 was achieved suggesting strong content validity (Polit & Beck, 2006).

Data collection was conducted through an online survey due to the nature of the study focusing on social media users. Google Forms or a similar platforms were used to distribute the questionnaire, which allowed for easy access and ensure respondents completed the survey at their convenience. Participants were recruited via word of mouth and targeted advertisements on social media platforms (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and WhatsApp) to reach users residing in Edo state. The survey link was included and an informed consent form explaining the purpose of the study, ensuring the voluntary nature of participation and confidentiality of responses.

The data collected from the online survey was analysed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 26.

Participants were informed that their responses will be anonymised and no personal identifying information will be collected. Respondents had the option to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty.

Data Presentation and Analysis

The instrument was administered on 400 respondents. However, 397 instruments were duly retrieved and deemed fit for analysis. The researcher subsequently utilised descriptive statistics for the analysis of data. The mainly likert scale response set which comprised mainly of strongly Agree, Agree, neutral, Disagree and Strongly Disagree response set were subsequently analyzed using mean and standard deviation.

Table 2: Demographic Profile of Respondents

Demographic Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Female	273	68.8%
	Male	124	31.2%
Age	18–20 years	3	0.8%
	26–30 years	145	36.5%
	36–40 years	57	14.4%
	46–50 years	58	14.6%

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Education	Undergraduate	18	4.5%
	First Degree/Diploma	181	45.6%
	Postgraduate Degree	198	49.9%
Religion	Christian	319	80.4%
	Muslim	73	18.4%
	African Traditional/Other	5	1.3%
Employment Status	Public/Private Sector	247	62.2%
	Self-Employed	110	27.7%
	Student	24	6.0%
	Unemployed	16	4.0%

The table 2 above reveals gender disparity among the respondents, with females (273) making up a significant majority at 68.8%, while males (124) constitute only 31.2%. This uneven distribution suggests that the data predominantly reflects a female perspective. The largest group of respondent falls within the 26–30 age bracket (145, 36.5%), followed by those aged 46–50 (58, 14.6%) and 36–40 (57, 14.4%). The younger age group of 18–20 years is notably underrepresented, with only (3, 0.8%) respondents, suggesting that the sample is skewed towards more mature individuals who may have more established viewpoints on governance and political issues. The majority of respondents hold a postgraduate degree (198, 49.9%), while a significant portion has a first degree or diploma (181, 45.6%). Only a small fraction (18, 4.5%) are undergraduates, indicating that the survey primarily represents a highly educated population whose responses may be shaped by their advanced academic exposure. A predominant majority of respondents identify as Christian (319, 80.4%), while Muslims account for a smaller segment (73, 18.4%). A minor proportion (5, 1.3%) adheres to African Traditional Religion or other beliefs, reflecting a religious composition that is not entirely diverse. The majority of respondents are employed in public or private sectors (247, 62.2%), followed by self-employed individuals (110, 27.7%). Students (24, 6.0%) and unemployed persons (16, 4.0%) make up the smaller segments, suggesting that the responses primarily reflect the views of working adults with direct stakes in governance matters.

Table 3: Responses on the Frequency of Engagement with Political and Governance Issues on Social Media

Frequency of Use	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision rule
I use social media daily to stay informed about political and governance issues.	397	3.6801	1.40019	Significant
I spend a significant amount of time on social media platforms discussing current events and governance."	397	3.0176	1.22976	Not Significant
I follow social media accounts	397	3.4005	1.17349	Not Significant

that focus on political or governmental matters.				
I regularly engage with news content shared by my social media contacts.	397	3.7834	1.38660	Significant
Frequency of Use aggregated	397	13.8816	3.06225	

The analysis of social media usage for political and governance-related engagement reveals interesting patterns in user behavior. A significant number of respondents indicated that they use social media daily to stay informed about political and governance issues (Mean = 3.68, Std. Deviation = 1.40). This suggests that social media plays an important role as a news source for political awareness. However, when it comes to actively discussing current events and governance, the responses were more neutral, with no significant trend observed (Mean = 3.02, Std. Deviation = 1.23). This implies that while people may consume political content, they are less likely to engage in conversations about it.

Similarly, following social media accounts that focus on political or governmental matters did not show a strong pattern (Mean = 3.40, Std. Deviation = 1.17), indicating that while some users do follow such accounts, it is not a widespread behavior. In contrast, engagement with news content shared by social media contacts was found to be significant (Mean = 3.78, Std. Deviation = 1.39), suggesting that people are more likely to interact with political information when it comes from their personal networks rather than official sources.

When looking at the overall frequency of social media use for political and governance-related activities, the aggregated measure shows a moderate level of engagement (Mean = 13.88, Std. Deviation = 3.06). This reflects a general trend of social media being a key medium for political information, though the level of participation varies among individuals. In summary, the findings suggest that while social media is a crucial platform for staying informed and engaging with shared content, users are less likely to participate in discussions or follow official political accounts. The relatively high standard deviations across responses indicate diverse behaviors, highlighting that while some individuals are highly engaged, others remain passive consumers of political content.

Table 4: Regression Analysis on the Relationship between Socio Demographic Factors and Frequency of Engagement with Governance on Social Media Variables Entered/Removed^b

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Religion, SEX, Age of Respondent , Educational Qualification of Respondents ^a		Enter

a. All requested variables entered.

b. Dependent Variable: FREQENG

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Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.404 ^a	.163	.154	.36934

a. Predictors: (Constant), Religion, SEX, Age of Respondent , Educational Qualification of Respondents

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	10.405	4	2.601	19.070	.000 ^a
	Residual	53.474	392	.136		
	Total	63.879	396			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Religion, SEX, Age of Respondent , Educational Qualification of Respondents

b. Dependent Variable: FREQENG

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	3.226	.309		10.425	.000
	SEX	-.422	.049	-.487	-8.615	.000
	Age of Respondent	.050	.017	.213	2.937	.004
	Educational Qualification of Respondents	-.294	.056	-.426	-5.209	.000
	Religion	.024	.043	.026	.570	.569

a. Dependent Variable: FREQENG

The regression analysis explores the relationship between demographic factors (sex, age, educational qualification, and religion) and engagement with political issues on social media (FREQENG). The results provide key insights into how different groups interact with political discussions online and highlight important trends in digital civic participation. The model shows a moderate relationship between the demographic variables and engagement with political issues on social media, with an R-value of 0.404. However, the R² value of 0.163 suggests that only 16.3% of the variation in engagement can be explained by these factors, meaning that other unexamined influences play a more significant role. Despite this, the model is statistically significant ($F(4,392) = 19.07, p < 0.001$), indicating that at least one of the predictors has a meaningful impact on online political engagement.

Discussion of Findings

The study found that women engage less frequently than men in political discussions on social media. Women may use social media for different purposes, such as social

interaction or entertainment, rather than political engagement. This aligns with Pearce & Rice (2020), who found that women are more active on platforms like Pinterest and Facebook, which are less politically oriented. Sociocultural norms and digital harassment may discourage women from participating in political discussions online. This is consistent with global trends where women face higher risks of online abuse, leading to lower participation in political discourse (Howard & Hussain, 2013). Pew Research (2021) found gender differences in platform preferences, with women favoring less politically charged platforms. This suggests that platform design and sociocultural factors play a role in shaping engagement patterns.

Older individuals (26–50 years) are more politically engaged on social media than younger individuals (18–20 years). Older individuals may use social media to stay informed about governance issues due to a greater sense of civic responsibility, while younger individuals may prioritise entertainment or lifestyle content. Older individuals may have more established viewpoints and a stronger interest in governance matters, leading to higher engagement. This aligns with Verba, Schlozman & Brady (1995), who found that political participation increases with age due to accumulated experience and resources. Greenwood and Perrin (2020) found that older adults predominantly use Facebook for political discussions, while younger adults gravitate towards platforms like Instagram and Snapchat, which are less politically oriented. Individuals with higher education levels engage less frequently in political discussions on social media. Highly educated individuals may have better access to information but may also be more critical of online political discourse, leading to lower engagement. This aligns with Norris (2001), who highlighted the second-level digital divide, where digital literacy and critical engagement vary across education levels. Highly educated individuals may feel disillusioned with the political system or skeptical of the impact of online discussions, leading to lower participation. This contradicts Pearce and Rice (2020), who found that higher education levels generally correlate with greater social media adoption. The study by Pearce and Rice (2020) found that higher education levels increase social media adoption, but this does not necessarily translate to political engagement, as seen in this study. Religion does not have a significant effect on political engagement on social media. Religious affiliation may not influence the motivations for using social media, as individuals may seek information or entertainment regardless of their religious beliefs. Political engagement may be driven more by factors such as age, gender, and education rather than religious affiliation. This aligns with Verba, Schlozman & Brady (1995), who found that resources and psychological engagement are more critical determinants of political participation. The study by Greenwood and Perrin (2020) did not find significant differences in social media usage based on religious affiliation, supporting the idea that religion plays a minimal role in shaping online political engagement. The study highlights the role of urban-rural disparities in social media adoption and engagement. Urban residents with better internet access and digital literacy are more likely to engage in governance discussions, while rural residents face barriers such as limited internet access and lower digital literacy (Norris, 2001). Accessibility to digital tools and

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resources is a critical factor in determining political engagement, as highlighted by Verba, Scholzman, & Brady (1995). Pearce and Rice (2020) found that urban residents are more engaged in online discussions compared to rural populations, indicating a digital divide in access and usage patterns.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study provides valuable insights into the demographic correlates of social media engagement with governance issues in Edo State. However, it also highlights the need for further research to explore the underlying causes of these trends, particularly the role of sociocultural factors, digital literacy and platform-specific behaviors. Future studies should incorporate qualitative methods to gain a deeper understanding of the motivations and barriers to engagement and explore strategies for bridging the digital divide and fostering inclusive political participation on social media. Policymakers and civic organisations should consider these findings when designing digital engagement strategies, ensuring that platforms are accessible, safe, and inclusive for all demographic groups. Efforts should be made to address gender disparities, increase youth participation, and re-engage highly educated individuals in governance discussions.

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